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CONVERSATION CIRCLE: TAKING CARE OF THOSE WHO CARE FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF “EMPOWERMENT” ATTITUDES

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ABSTRACT

Reflect on the historicity of Disability and the vision of disability in the present day, where disability is no longer considered a disease but a condition. potentialities and the inclusion of People with Disabilities. This article aims to describe the experiences of an institution in Niterói, dedicated to the care of people with intellectual disabilities and multiple disabilities, the Associação de Pais e Amigos do Excepcionais (APAE – NITERÓI), which experiences the transformation, by developing a process of joint reconstruction work, involving the main actors of care in the rehabilitation process, involving the Person with Disability, the family and health professionals, to favor social inclusion. As the main device for building this paradigmatic transformation, the technical team has been producing several Rounds of Conversations, with the different actors in this process to reflect on the theme of capacitism and the obstacles to social inclusion. The Conversation Wheel Project defines its mission, goals and objectives based on welcoming families. Thus, by articulating with the institution's professionals, prevention actions, guidance and establishment of support groups for parents, intending to improve the quality of life of these families. By creating spaces for exchanges between parents, administrators and professionals, sociability and the ability of these groups to participate in the institution are increased, thus expanding everyone's commitment to the full development of the patient, in their particularities and favoring the social inclusion and neutralizing capacitist actions.

Keywords: Capacitance. Deficiency. Conversation Wheel.

INTRODUCTION

Disability is not a disease, it is a condition. It is urgently necessary to change the point of view and understand that places are deficient, ideas are deficient, our ways of teaching and the solutions that society insists on doing even if it knows, does not include all people. A less capable society is one that thinks of all people, including those with disabilities, who are not heroes or victims of their condition, but capable and productive subjects within their potential and equivalence.

For Mello (2014), ableism is the materialization of attitudes permeated by prejudice that categorize subjects according to the adequacy of their bodies to an ideal of beauty and functional capacity. It is a concept present in the social that evaluates people with disabilities as unequal, less able or incapable of managing their own lives, being for the ableists, disability as a diminished state of the human being. It is a form of subliminal prejudice embedded in social symbolic production, showing a universalized construction of oppression on the understanding of disability (DIAS, 2013).

There are indications since prehistoric times that man already lived with disability. Over the century, people with disabilities have been involved in narratives of abandonment, rejection, many different narratives. First, for not having the same rhythm when we were nomadic people, then for not having the perfect, beautiful and strong body as the Greeks conceptualized. At a given moment, people with disabilities are seen as aberrations, "God's punishment" and then labeled as sick and treated as they are until the present day.

In this social historical context and given the complexity that is the process of rehabilitation to inclusion, the present study aims to demonstrate how, by adjusting and innovating different care actions in their work processes, APAE - Niterói, an institution in the city of Niterói that serves People with Intellectual Disabilities and Multiple Disabilities, seeks to transform perspectives and promote reflections, having as a methodology the implementation of the Conversation Circle device, addressing various themes for the promotion of technical intervention actions to help families, expanding attention also to care who takes care of. Believing that by offering this care, a critical

reflection on the situations experienced by families that have a person with a disability at their core is promoted, and that the perception of the dimensions of care is favored, resuming the role of the family, redirecting care and providing tools for the family to build new plans, eliminating the barriers of ability.

Capacitism

Reflecting on the historicity of Disability and the vision of disability in the present day, it is understood that ableism is constituted as a designation, as it designates prejudiced attitudes towards people with disabilities.

According to Guimarães (2013), the designation is considered as the meaning of a name as its relationship with other names and with the world, historically cut by the name. The designation is not something abstract, but linguistic and historical.

According to the above, we can highlight the definition of ableism, present in the Glossary of terms related to accessibility and disability of the Chamber of Deputies:

Capacitism: act of discrimination, prejudice or oppression against a person with a disability. It is an attitudinal barrier. In general, it occurs when someone considers a person incapable, due to differences and bodily impediments. Capacitism is focused on the supposed 'capacities of people without disabilities' as a reference to show the supposed 'limitations of people with disabilities'. In ableism, emphasis is placed on the supposed 'capable people', who make up the majority of the population and are supposedly considered 'normal'.

Starting from the logic of prejudice, we observed that ableism alludes to an unfavorable opinion about the person with a disability, a previous opinion, often based on the imaginary about the person with a disability, in which he is seen as someone without the ability to have autonomy and independence to manage their own lives (MARCHESAN, et al, 2021).

Also according to MARCHESAN, et al, seeing the disabled person in a preconceived and limiting view comes from a socio-historical constitution

of thoughts that underlie a series of prejudices, because it presupposes that these subjects have limitations that disable them in all instances of life, causing their capabilities to be suppressed by a totalizing and excluding discourse.

Historically contextualizing, disability is described in the subjects' bodies and its understanding has gone through various configurations, from religious and supernatural conceptions, through the biomedical model, to the biopsychosocial model, which overlaps in national and international legislation. It started from the integrationist discourse, in the which person with disabilities must adapt to society, to the inclusive discourse, when there is a process of adjustment of both the person with disability and society. According to Aranha (2001), the difference between integration and inclusion lies in the fact that, while the former emphasizes the "readiness" of the subject for life in the community", the later invests in the development of the subject and in the creation of conditions that guarantee the access and participation of people with disabilities in society, through supports, whether physical, psychological, or yet another.

Therefore, social inclusion happens when there is an adjustment process for both the person with a disability and society. Inclusion is an open process, it is something to be built together and that still needs planning, experimentation because its improvement is necessary for future generations. (SPIDER, 2001).

In his studies, Aranha (2001) also mentions that both must act together for inclusion to take place in social practice, as there are interventions both in the subject's development process and in the social readjustment process.

However, in today's society, still a large part of social initiatives are directed to a universal subject, commonly represented by the "standard" and idealized man, and the exclusion, in this way, the denial of all human diversity. Medeiros and Mudado (2010) explain that, by denying the ethical imperatives of responsibility and commitment to human beings, social exclusion is tinged with prejudice by affirming an ideal of a biologically perfect man.

In fact, inclusion requires a long trajectory, with a view to transforming everyone's social practice.

In this study, we describe the experience of an institution in Niterói, dedicated to the care of people with intellectual disabilities and multiple disabilities, the Associação de Pais e Amigos do Excepcional (APAE – Niterói), which experiences this transformation by developing a work process of joint reconstruction, involving the main actors of care in the rehabilitation process, starring the Person with Disabilities, the family and health professionals, to favor social inclusion.

Faced with the complexity of the process from rehabilitation to inclusion, it is necessary to adjust and innovate different care actions, as well as to apply comprehensive care on its various fronts, seeking to unite health, care and education actions, based on the disability care policy. As a result, the institution has been structuring and reorganizing its actions, with the objective of promoting the leading role of people with disabilities, through activities for the development of their potential; of education and information for the development of the subject, with actions aimed at self-defense. And in parallel, the work of assistance to family members, which provide the trust and credibility of People with Disabilities (PwD), respecting their limits and their diversity, in order to minimize the barriers imposed by the ability.

As the main device for the construction of this paradigmatic transformation, the technical team has been producing several Conversation Rounds, with the different actors of this process to reflect on the theme of capacitism and the obstacles to social inclusion.

In this study, we will pay attention to Conversation Wheel produced with the families of those assisted with intellectual disabilities in follow-up at APAE-Niterói.

The family as an agency of socialization, protection and participation.

The family is the main agent of primary socialization and where care relationships are produced between its members through protection, reception, respect for individuality and empowerment of the other. In each family, there are values transmitted from generation to generation, involving affection and identity.

The family to which the disabled person belongs

plays an important role in opposing their marginalization. It has the important function of providing to make the desiring subject, a person who can transform their impulses into desires, seeking to fulfill them within the framework of their difference and through it.

The response that the family will give to this challenge will depend on past experiences, economic situation, as well as ethnic background and family relationships, among other influences, which, in turn, will determine whether the challenge of creating, caring for and educating their child will be faced. The family may have difficulties in fulfilling its social role of educating individuals to actively participate in today's society that emphasizes aspects such as efficiency and effectiveness.

Social work with Families finds its ethical and political foundations in the Federal Constitution of 1988; in the Organic Law of Social Assistance, of 1993; in the National Policy for Social Assistance, 2004; reaffirming the adoption of the centrality of the family as a structuring element of the offers of social assistance and respecting the different forms of organization of families.

The actions of this work involve the recognition of the organization of the family's daily life, the exercise of roles and functions in the family, the relationships with the disability, the relationships of authority and affection; the values, representations and practices of care and socialization of its members and also the coexistence.

Families develop their own mechanisms to face the challenges in caring for the person with a disability, these mechanisms vary according to culturally installed beliefs and with offers and availability of resources. Faced with this new situation, it is very likely that there will be a shock, a disbelief; Families can become tense, disorganized, conflicted, and even break up with the separation of the parents, or even the "forgetfulness" of the other child.

Therefore, it is necessary to adopt a clear methodological approach, which promotes a critical reflection on the situations experienced by families that have a person with a disability at their core, and favors the perception of dimensions and minimizes the consequences of ableism.

We seek methodological approaches that can meet the demands through spaces that promote technical intervention actions to help families.

METHODOLOGY

Conversation circle approach with families

Conversation circles are collective spaces used for discussion and reflection on various topics, and can be used for different purposes, including action planning. Where families report their experiences. Based on the conversation circle methodology, the context for planning technical actions that can help these families is developed.

The themes are previously defined together with a psychologist who accompanies the conversation circle, begins with the presentation of the participants, the topic to be addressed and a reflection message lasts for approximately 40 minutes being held fortnightly. During the conversation, the technical team makes observations regarding the participants' reports where all the information is analyzed and directed.

Conversation solidifies a practice in which social representations are respected in a conflictive, cooperative and consensus-building environment, minimizing resistance to listening, reflecting and analyzing the problems presented by families. In the different relationships of everyday life, the peculiar aspects of each place are characterized in its historical, political and cultural context that will facilitate the apprehension of new ways of thinking, acting, doing and promoting knowledge through words, gestures and acts.

CASE STUDY - CONVERSATION WHEEL

Theme: who takes care of who cares?

Theme presented in partnership with APAE - Niterói and Anhanguera College in the conversation circle for the families of those assisted by the APAE institution, the psychology students of the college accompanied by the course coordinator and the teacher along with the team that monitors the families of those assisted by the institution social worker and psychologist.

After presenting the theme, a report caught the attention of the group that was participating, a mother reports her story that after receiving the information that her son had Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) after a period of almost two years in search of a diagnosis, went through a grieving process, because the initial idea she had of pregnancy would be a “normal” baby like most other mothers, she needed to rediscover the joy of being a mother and how to love that child with the same love that a mother receives. your child in your arms being a special child on the autism spectrum, the period of acceptance was very difficult. She decided to give up her teaching profession to dedicate herself fully to monitoring her son so that he could have access to all possible treatments aiming at a better quality of life in the expectation that at some point she could resume her routine including her work, according to this mother’s report, she was unable to resume her professional life, the process is very difficult, little help from the family, difficult access to support networks, the waiting time is very long and there is little access to information. She lives alone with her son, she reports that in many moments she feels tired, she does not see herself as a warrior, as she often hears this speech from people, but says that she did not choose to live this life experience, she came to her and learned to deal with and accept it. and that doesn’t change her joy in being a mother. Today her biggest dream is to see her son happy and included in society without prejudice, just being different.

In this report it was possible to identify many social and emotional difficulties in the family structure, there is the financial issue due to the mother not having the structural conditions to work, depending on the social benefits that often take time to be accessed, a woman who cancels herself in social life and professional to dedicate exclusively to the child without the help of the father, an intense routine of comings and goings in search of treatments for the child, not allowing them to have a social life such as leisure, culture etc..., the difficulties of accessing information, doctors, medication when necessary, sport, therapeutic accompaniments and inclusive school for the social and cognitive development of this child.

This report was only possible because this mother could have a space to talk about her experience, feeling confident that there would be no kind of

prejudice, criticism or judgment.

The team that accompanied the conversation circle can provide guidance when necessary to the mother for access to care networks, providing psychological support at no cost to the mother by the faculty psychology team and strengthening the bond of this mother with the institution so that she has support for the continuity of monitoring the child at the institution and support of the team in care for the family at the institution such as family reception, lectures, social and technical meetings. The institution APAE-Niterói holds fortnightly conversation circles coordinated by the social worker and psychologist who serve the families.

Conversation circles allow families to have a voice in this space, feeling part of the group, choices and decisions. Also an opportunity to work on listening to others, respecting different opinions.

According to Geraldi “[...] the stories that make us unique and ‘go repeatable’. Uncertain uniqueness, because if I understand with words that, before being mine, were and are also someone else’s, I will never be sure if I am speaking or if something speaks for me [...]”. (GERALDI, 2005, p. 22).

Within family relationships, ableism can also occur, which often manifests itself implicitly, when family members in a protectionist way consider people with disabilities as incapable subjects, developing speeches and actions that harm and frustrate the development of their autonomy and disrespect their desires and emotions, often taking away the right to answer about their own desires and desires, without a voice and no time to resolve certain situations in their life. It is in this context that the Institution APAE Niterói identified the importance of discussing the place of speech in demystifying the existence of a universal subject, who believes that all people start from a common position of access to speech and listening (MONBAÇA, 2017). The aim is to resume the role of the family, redirecting care, providing tools for the family to build new plans, or adjust old dreams to suit the new script of life, for her and consequently for her children.

Understanding ableism as prejudice against people with disabilities, as they define subjects and bodies from a standardized reference as a “normal” body,

one of the forms of this oppression reveals itself in society through attitudinal barriers. These are defined, according to current legislation, as any obstacle, obstacle, attitude or behavior that limits or prevents the person's social participation, as well as the enjoyment, fruition and exercise of their rights to accessibility, freedom of movement and expression, communication, access to information, understanding, safe circulation, among others.

In this sense, attitudinal barriers are established in the social field, where human relationships focus on the limitations of individuals and not on their potential, attitudes or behaviors that prevent or impair the social participation of people with disabilities in equal conditions and opportunities with others. the other subjects.

Amaral (1988) explains attitudinal barrier as a defense interspersed between two people, where one is in a certain more favorable position in relation to the other.

CONCLUSION

When spaces for exchanges are created between parents and between them and administrators and professionals, we are increasing sociability and the ability of these groups to participate in the institution itself, thus expanding everyone's commitment to the full development of the patient, in their particularities. and favoring social inclusion and neutralizing enabling actions.

The Conversation Wheel Project defines its mission, goals and objectives based on the service to welcome families. Thus, by articulating with the institution's professionals, prevention actions, guidance and establishment of support groups for parents, the aim is to improve the quality of life of these families.

In conversation circles, when we use a different perspective to analyze the actions of families, we are able to envision possible paths in the direction of making the meeting attractive and the family as the protagonist. In this way, we can say that the development of a good practice is done in listening and looking, articulated with significant learning, which add greater meaning and significance to the family as a subject.

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FREUD AND PIAGET IN THE CLASSROOM : HOW TRANSFERENCE INTERRELATES WITH CONSTRUCTIVISM, COMPOSING A NEW CONCEPTION OF EDUCATION.

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INTRODUCTION

How to encourage learning through understanding the existing relationship between Freudian Transference ideas and Piagetian Constructivism in the teacher-student dichotomy in the classroom?

The pedagogical coordinator has a fundamental role in breaking paradigms in relation to learning difficulties, including school failure rates. The relationship between the teacher and his students, with the awareness of unconscious Freudian transference relationships, will be one more point in facilitating learning and in motivating students for this learning. It is the fundamental role of the coordinator to facilitate and mediate this relationship.

Faced with a current situation in Brazil of low learning rates, a large number of students held back in the first grades of elementary school, this research seeks some directions on the possibilities of reversing, or some reduction, of this situation.

I believe that this study can help to draw the attention of school administrators to the need to prepare teachers more and better, not only from an intellectual point of view, in terms of content domains and classroom practice, but also to equip them with attitudes of sensitivity and understanding of human unconscious relationships and reactions.

Freud once told one of his biographers that there are three “impossible” professions: psychoanalyzing, governing and educating (Gay, 1991). Like all catchphrases, this one was also intended to provoke surprise and make one reflect. In this case, the “impossibility” concerns the fact that human beings are endowed with freedom and initiative, which is why they will never completely submit to authority, whatever it may be.

Thus, the phrase warned against the abusive pretensions of the educator (read pedagogical team), the ruler and the psychoanalyst, who believed they were omnipotent and capable of molding the other to their image and likeness.

It is impossible to completely psychoanalyze someone, as the unconscious will continue to exist and expand with or without psychoanalysis. Nor is it impossible to educate someone completely, as the subject will continue to learn until the last breath

of his life (perhaps after this moment...), or to govern absolutely, as there has always been and will be opposition, even if it is depreciated, such as “dumb”, or silenced at the point of the rifle.

Freud was wise not to add to his list of impossibilities that an idea be interpreted literally and considered as indisputable truth, because it was formulated by a “demigod”. Because his ideas would have exactly this destiny, especially in the part related to educating. Psychoanalysis would have nothing to say to educators, given that their activity would extend between the useless and the harmful: useless because “it is impossible to educate” (Freud dixit), and harmful because education would be, intrinsically, violence against children’s minds; and the more apparently liberal, the more harmful, because the more lying. (Gay, 1991)

In this article, I seek exactly to follow the opposite path, perhaps controversial, but certainly daring. There is a guideline that seeks to bring up issues purposely forgotten by managers, educators and thinkers, such as the undeniable existence of the unconscious and its uncontrollable movements.

I try here to raise questions more than to answer them, creating a certain initial discomfort characteristic for those looking for ready-made solutions. They don’t exist. But there are the accumulated experiences, pains and pleasures of those who venture into the world of Education and its challenging management.

I seek to resume the close relationships between science and socialization, to remake the ties between Psychoanalysis and Education, highlighting transference relationships - a concept that I address in the first chapter of this work - in the teacher-student relationship. I take as guiding threads the following questions:

- What, in the relationship between educator and student, conveys and actually interferes with learning?
- How do transference relationships existing in the classroom interfere with students’ learning?
- How can the teacher act positively on these transference reactions and relationships in the classroom, in order to promote a new education?
- What are the points of intersection between Freud’s and Piaget’s ideas about education? Can the

clinic meet with the school?

Well, it was to be expected that a teacher would not use transference and countertransference as a work tool, as occurs in psychoanalysis offices, but teachers, without realizing it, are objects of transference by their students and these, objects of countertransference by teachers. .

Within a classroom, learning and conflicts often occur as a result of this representation attributed to the other. It is not by chance that “preferences” occur and that some students are loved or not, by different teachers and vice versa. It is interesting to see in a class council that opinions differ between teachers when referring to the same class, which for some is unbearable and for others, docile and friendly. There are students who cannot learn with a certain teacher, but with another, of the same subject, they are able to shine in their performance. This is a controversial and serious issue!

Could many of the problems in Education be a consequence of these poorly worked links within the school? Normally we do not have professionals who can work in these relationships to solve them. In the Educational Guidance sectors, the professionals’ greatest concern is with the performance of their students and their possible consequences: failure, retirement, evasion, etc. There are no professionals concerned with assessing or diagnosing the impasses that are created in these “love-hate relationships”: Who would these teachers represent to their students and who would these students be to their teachers? Any figure that represents authority for the student, whether a child, youth or adult, will always be perceived in a particular and individual way. They are usually experiences from the past of each individual who “chooses” the other to deposit their demands or sometimes to contain the affections of the past. This is one of the biggest problems that occur in classrooms and that few realize. If everyone were guided and aware, major problems could be avoided and the school could become the object of desire of each of its visitors, transforming learning into something pleasurable for teachers and students. (Bacha, 1998)

One of the reasons for considering student learning assessments as being arbitrary and incomplete is to think about the possibility of failing some “geniuses” who did not adapt to certain teachers or cer-

tain schools. A failure can be catastrophic for the self-esteem of a child or young person, who, due to this partial result, may give up fighting and continue their studies, or start to present emotional disorders of the most varied kind. The status quo of the teacher will be assured and the repeating children will almost always be responsible for their difficulties. Even if the reasons for the deficit are just maladjustment or (unconscious) disagreements in their relationships with their peers or with the school environment. Many times, the teacher who has not been able to transmit his knowledge, having a scant foundation of psychological theories on education, feels that his hands are absolutely tied to revert this situation.

A brief explanation about one of the unconscious movements that most interferes in human relationships – Transference – may help in understanding the process of “intimacy” that is being built in classrooms, especially in schools whose philosophy is Constructivism – a concept about which I will deal with in the second chapter - as they promote a greater and closer relationship between the individuals involved in the educational duality - the teacher and the student.

Saying that teaching is difficult, that teachers have a complex and arduous task before them, which is not restricted only to the formative aspect within the classroom, but includes aspects of management and handling of human relations in the context of the school, it would be risking that they would consider me, at the very least, unoriginal. But, I will take this risk. I think that only from an analysis of what this complexity involves, the questions it poses and the requirements to be observed by the answers itS demands, it seems possible to me to offer an adjusted vision of what can be expected from an explanatory framework of the teaching and learning processes. learning and Pedagogical Coordination.

Brief Concept of Transference

Transference was of fundamental importance for the development of psychoanalysis. And on it, Freud dedicated several years of his work and life. It was also presented as one of the bases of psychoanalysis, as not only is it one of the essential instruments of therapeutic action, but because it constitutes a way of passing from practice to theory. It is an

instrument of irreplaceable value, as it gives us the opportunity to know and investigate the patient's unconscious and inaccessible material. At the same time, it is one of the greatest risks for the treatment, as it awakens resistance that becomes our greatest obstacle during the course of the analysis.

Transference does not only occur in the analytic situation, it is not the exclusive domain of psychoanalysis. Several other lines of work use the term TRANSFERENCE, giving it another connotation and another treatment. Transference exists in other psychotherapies, with the difference that it is neither recognized nor analysed.

Transference occurs in analysis or outside it, in neurotics, psychotics and "normal people". All human relationships contain a mix of transference and realistic reactions. All people have transference reactions, the analytic situation only facilitates their development and uses them for interpretation and reconstruction. The analyst is the ideal target for transference reactions; but so are all the important people in an individual's life.

In Freud's theoretical texts, "The Dynamics of Transference" occupies an essential place in the sense of systematically explaining transference. In this text Freud tries to elucidate the reason why the transference inevitably arises during the analysis and plays a fundamental role in the treatment.

The psychoanalytic transference expresses a conflict between the patient and the therapist, as Freud explains in 1912:

Unconscious feelings try to avoid the recognition that the treatment requires; they aim, on the contrary, at reproduction, with all the power of hallucination and the lack of knowledge of time, characteristic of the unconscious. As in dreams, the patient gives course and reality to what results from the awakening of his unconscious feelings; tends to vent his emotions without taking into account the reality of the situation. The physician requires him to place his emotions in their proper place in the treatment and history of his life, to subject them to rational consideration, and to appreciate them at their true psychic value. This fi-

ght between the doctor and the patient, between the intellect and the forces of instinct, between recognition and the aspiration for discharge, takes place almost entirely in the field of transference (p.100) .

As Freud wrote in 1910, transference occurs throughout the entire analytic treatment, it is a special objective relationship that is established between the doctor and the patient that surpasses all rational measure, ranging from the most affectionate abandonment to the most tenacious hostility, taking from the patient all his peculiarities of previous, unconscious erotic attitudes.

Transference is a type of object relation with a person, in a main characteristic way, it is the experience of feelings in relation to a person of the present, which is not addressed to this one, which is actually the other of the past. (GREENSON, 1981)

It is, therefore, perfectly normal and understandable that the load of libido that the partially dissatisfied individual keeps hopefully at the ready is also oriented towards the person of the doctor (therapist).

This load will adhere to certain models, including the doctor in one of the psychic series that the patient has formed up until then.

Transference for Freud (1912) is originally a special case of displacement of affect from one representation to another. In his first writings on the subject, Freud reveals how the individual's relationship with parental figures is revived in transference, he underlines that transference is linked to "imagos" (mainly maternal, paternal and fraternal imago).

The objects that were the original sources of the transference relationship are the important people of a child's early life. In general, purveyors of love, comfort, or punishment. However transference reactions can be originated from figures of the present. But analysis will show that these later objects are secondary and themselves out (transferred) from early childhood figures.

This extension of the notion of transference, structure of psychoanalytic treatment, according to childhood conflicts, results in the definition of the

concept of “transference neurosis”. Says Freud, “if we manage to give all the symptoms of the disease a new meaning, to replace his common neurosis with a transference neurosis, this patient can be cured by therapeutic work” (1914, p. 154) .

During an analysis one can notice the patient’s growing interest in his analyst. If the transference situation is handled properly, it is possible to give a new transference meaning to all the symptoms of the illness and to replace its “habitual neurosis” with a “transference neurosis”.

In “Studies on Hysteria” (1895) Freud writes that this new symptom (transference) which was produced according to the old model, must be treated in the same way as the old symptoms.

The “transference neurosis” assumes all aspects of the patient’s illness, but it is an artificial illness and is accessible to the analyst’s intervention. It’s a new edition of an old disease.

We are basically dealing here with transference in the neurotic, where it is seen as involving three persons in all: the individual, an object from the past, and an object from the present. For this it is necessary to have a clear differentiation between the I and the external OBJECT. The neurotic patient is able to separate his EGO (self) from external objects, being able to transfer contents from one object to another, as explained by Greenson :

Neurotic transference phenomena are based on the individual’s ability to differentiate between his/her I (self) and the object world; and the willingness to shift reactions from a representation of the past to one of the present. For there to be transference and his return to reality, there must be a neurotic patient capable of temporarily acting in a transferential way, clearly distinguishing his analyst from the transferred figure. (1981, p. 192)

Transference reactions demonstrate the egoic stability of the neurotic patient. Neurotic transference phenomena show that the patient has a stable representation of his Ego, which is profoundly different from his object representations (GREENSON, 1981). When the neurotic patient transfers to the present, displaces and re-edits contents of the past, this only happens partially and temporarily, as Gre-

enson explains :

Regression in ego functions is limited to certain aspects of your relationship to the transference figure and is reversible. The patient during a transference reaction temporarily and partially abandons some of his reality-testing functions, which are then taken up again. (1981, p. 199)

Basically for this reason, Freud (1916-1917) says that essentially narcissistic people will not be able to maintain a firm transference relationship that can be analyzed. The relationship of these people with the analyst will be full of fusions of the I (self) and object images (GREENSON, 1981). It could be said that this individual projects most of the time as a form of transference. He projects representations of his I (self) onto the person of the analyst, making other types of transference reactions difficult. These projections made by the patients are representations, in fact, repetitions of something experienced in the past by the patient, as will be seen later on .

Brief Constructivist Vision of Teaching-Learning

The existence of the school institution is something so inherent to our society and our way of life that, sometimes, we do not ask ourselves why there is a school or we give this question a little simple answers: “to distract the children”, “to reproduce established culture”.

Just as we cannot understand human development without culture, we will hardly be able to understand it without considering the diversity of educational practices through which we can access and interpret this culture in a personal way, practices in which school practices should be included. Through these practices, an attempt is made to ensure a planned and systematic intervention, aimed at promoting certain aspects of the development of boys and girls.

The concern with a static and alienating school has been a constant among thinkers from different disciplines, who have drawn attention to other social institutions.

As far as the school is concerned, denying its social and socializing character seems quite absurd; in

fact that is one of the reasons for its existence. With regard to the student, the explanations that inserted him in a merely reactive plane, or even passive, in the face of what is offered to him as a learning object, are long gone.

School education promotes development as it promotes the student's constructive mental activity, responsible for transforming him into a unique person, in the context of a determined social group.

The constructivist conception of learning starts from the obvious fact that the school makes cultural aspects accessible to its students that are fundamental for their personal development, and not only in the cognitive sphere; education is the engine for global development, and this also means including personal balance, social insertion, interpersonal and motor skills.

The constructivist conception also starts from a consensus that is already quite ingrained in relation to the active nature of learning, which leads to the acceptance that this is the result of a personal construction, but in which not only the subject who learns intervenes; the significant "others", the cultural agents, are essential pieces for this personal construction, for this development to which we allude.

Learning contributes to development insofar as learning is not copying or reproducing reality. For the constructivist conception, we learn when we are able to elaborate a personal representation about an object of reality or content that we intend to learn. (Coll & Solé, 2003, page 20)

This elaboration implies the approximation between the individual and the object or content, but it is not an empty approximation, starting from nothing, but rather, from the experiences, interests and previous knowledge that can account for the "novelty". With the previously acquired meanings that the individual already has, he approaches the new aspect, which will only seem new, but which in fact will be able to perfectly interpret it. At other times, the subject-learner will be faced with a challenge to which he will try to respond by modifying the meanings with which he was already provided. In this process, not only is what he already has modified, but he also interprets the new in a particular

way, in order to integrate it and make it his own. (COLL, 2003)

When this process occurs, it is said that significant learning has occurred. It is clear that this is not a process of accumulating new knowledge, but the integration, modification, establishment of relationships and coordination between schemes of knowledge that the student already possesses, endowed with a certain structure and organization that varies, in links and relationships, with each learning that the individual performs. I make it clear that meaningful learning is not finished learning (if there is such a thing!), but it can always be improved. To the same extent, this learning will be significantly memorized and will be functional, useful to continue learning.

School contents constitute an important point in this discussion, as they appear in the framework of the constructivist conception as a crucial element for understanding, articulating, analyzing and innovating teaching practice. It should be mentioned that these contents, whatever they may be, are already elaborated and are part of culture and knowledge, which makes the construction of students a peculiar construction. Something is built that already exists, which naturally does not prevent construction (in the sense we give it: assigning personal meaning), although it forces it to be carried out in a certain sense, precisely the one that points to social convention in relation to the concrete content. I.e.,

[...] it is not about students adding up approximately as established, or putting the "agá" where they think it is best. Although, obviously, they can, in their process, "invent" very interesting ways of adding up, which can lead them to unexpected results; although they can use spelling in a highly creative and unconventional way, it is obvious that this personal construction must be oriented towards getting closer to the culturally established, understanding it and being able to use it in multiple and varied ways. (SOLÉ, 2003, page 22)

And this is one of the reasons why the construction of students cannot be carried out alone, as nothing would guarantee that their orientation would be adequate, that would allow their progress. There is another reason, much more important in my view:

construction itself cannot be ensured alone, as Coll shows us:

[...] the constructivist conception assumes a whole set of postulates around the consideration of teaching as a joint, shared process, in which the student, thanks to the help he receives from the teacher, can progressively show himself competent and autonomous in solving problems. tasks, the use of concepts, the practice of certain attitudes and numerous questions. (2003, p. 22)

In this way, the child builds more or less significant learning, not only because he has certain knowledge, nor because the contents are this or that; he builds on what was said and on the help he receives from his teacher, both to use his personal baggage and to progress in his appropriation. "In fact, we could say that the help of the teacher, the guidance he offers and the autonomy he allows, is what makes it possible for the student to construct meanings." (COLL, 2003, p.)

I will now summarize some of the main characteristics of teacher-student interaction processes in the classroom which, according to current knowledge of the Constructivist Theory of Piaget and Vygotsky, are involved in the teaching-learning processes (Coll, 1984, 1986 , 1990, 1991; Solé, 1990; Vygotsky, 1979 in Onrubia , 2003) and which I have treated so far.

1- Insert as much as possible the punctual activity carried out by the student at each moment within the framework of broader milestones or objectives, in which this activity can acquire meaning in the most appropriate way.

2- To enable, to the highest possible degree, the participation of all students in the different activities and tasks, even if their level of competence, their interest or their knowledge are at first very scarce and not adequate.

3- Establish an affective and emotional relationship climate based on trust, security and mutual acceptance, in which curiosity, the capacity for surprise and interest in knowledge fit.

4- Introduce, as far as possible, specific modifications and adjustments, both in the broader program and in the concrete development of the performance itself, depending on the information obtained from the performances and partial products performed by the students.

5- Promote the autonomous use and deepening of the knowledge that students are learning.

6- To establish, to the greatest possible extent, constant and explicit relationships between the new contents that are the object of learning and the students' prior knowledge.

7- Use language as clearly and explicitly as possible, trying to avoid and control possible misunderstandings or misunderstandings.

8- Use language to recontextualize and reconceptualize experience.

School learning is a complex process that fully involves students. It is the students who learn. However, making this possible is a collective adventure.

Firstly, because society is an entity that is continually demanding in relation to the capabilities of all those who compose it, and with that it contributes to fulfilling our own demands.

Secondly, because culture (uses, customs, knowledge of different types and values), in a way, makes us who we are, and being able to appropriate it, critically review it and contribute to its renewal presupposes, by its time, we take responsibility for the elaboration of our identity.

And, thirdly, because, as Tereza Mauri says, " without the contribution of teachers aware that knowledge is a construction, school learning would be an uncertain journey, with dubious consequences " .

From Piaget to Freud: from knowledge to desire; from repression to pleasure

Today we witness different attempts to unite Freud and Piaget. Many questions arise in this sense: why, without Piaget, does psychoanalysis seem to lose the right to enter the school institution? Why does Piaget seem to be the passport that the psychoa-

nalyst must take to cross the frontiers of the clinic and enter the fields of education? Why, without Piaget, any psychoanalytic incursion into these “foreign lands” seems marked by the weight of “illegal” and “illegitimacy”?

Could it be that by reconciling Freud with Piaget, wouldn't we be imposing limits to Psychoanalysis that belong to Psychology?

Returning to Neill's perspective, which intensely explored the Freedom x Content opposition and made it the axis of his pedagogical proposal, teaching came to be the “curse that blinds thousands of teachers”. And in his contempt for the intellectual, he was said to be a supporter of Freud.

If it were true that Freud only cared about affection and that it is separate from the intellectual, could there be any objection to seeking to complete it with Genetic Epistemology today, when “alternative” proposals are being tempered by a revaluation of knowledge?

A union like this, despite seeking to pacify a field whose professional coexistence is usually guided by belligerence, nevertheless suggests that psychoanalysis could not offer a properly epistemological contribution. Intellectual and social goods would be attributed to psychology's possession, leaving psychoanalysis with affective assets (Bacha, 1998, p. 107).

It seeks to bring back knowledge to the school through the hands of Piaget, because he is recognized as an authority with regard to knowledge and its acquisition process. “The analysis of the convergence of cognition and affectivity” is “an effervescent theme of the psychopedagogical current” that is “continuously faced with the duality: genetic epistemology and psychoanalysis”, as Dolle writes (1993, p. 8).

It seems that psychoanalysis is forced to share the same theoretical framework, somewhat limited and limiting, as psychologies, which first separate and then oppose an affect/individual/inside and an intellect/social/outside, confining psychoanalysis to the clinic . .

Bachelard , in his work, has been describing the recognition of the psychoanalytic contribution, since

the beginning of the last century, to the universe of Epistemology: “the psychoanalysis of objective knowledge”. Analytical work has been adding its dimension of imaginary creation to epistemology, offering a way of seeing knowledge that is strongly influenced by emotions and unconscious affections.

The “psychoanalysis of objective knowledge” reveals the positivity of the false and the imaginary in the “epistemological obstacles” that the historical movement of the sciences “rectify”. It is a different conception of knowledge and objectivity than the purely Piagetian theses offer us.” (Bachelard , 1977, pg. 98)

Lajonquière , a French psychoanalyst, claims not to be a unifier of Freud and Piaget, but takes the contributions of the Swiss master as a starting point for a reflection on the learning process that he articulates with Oedipus and Castration. This could be one of the many “psychoanalytic conceptions of education”.

Psychoanalysis and genetic psychology, says Lajonquière , are today “two poles of obligatory reference” in psychology and pedagogy, both having become “solid theoretical-practical paradigms to which, out of habit, the right to thinking about affectivity, the first, and intelligence the second” (1993, p. 116).

He himself did not intend to unite them by expanding the limits of Piagetian psychology, in order to make it embrace the affectivity that Freud studied, because it is already there. It is not enough to simply expand the “original paradigmatic limits of genetic psychology in such a way as to include the (mis) so-called ‘affectivity’ in it”. Because “the problem is not in the fact that Piaget has ignored affectivity, but in the way it is understood” (1993, p. 120).

Reason x Affectivity dichotomy , it is “necessary to discard the terms factors, aspects and variables once and for all when referring to affectivity and intelligence”, because, if we accept them, we will “unfailingly fall into the trap of trying to conceptualize the nature and circumstances of the (inter) relation between these kinds of pre-constituted entities” (1993, p. 119).

Lajonquière wants to make an “epistemological

break' within the classic (psycho) pedagogical tradition", whose hallmark, he says, is empiricism. He wants to think "in an anti-empiricist way the learning processes". "Faced with the bazaar of psychology", there are only two "vaccines to counteract the vicious action of empiricism and psychological substantialism: Piaget's genetic psychology and Freudian- Lacanian psychoanalysis" (1993, p. 144).

These two "antidotes" are indispensable for thinking about the reconstruction of concepts about the acquisition of knowledge and educational institutions, in a way that is not based on the empirical data apprehended by the senses.

From Piagetian psychology, we will borrow "equilibration", without which it is considered impossible to think, among others, the "psychogenesis of socially shared logical-mathematical categories", for example. But it is insufficient and falls short when it comes to conceptualizing the "dramatic subjectivity" that describes the particularities of the different subjects in this reconstructive process.

To think psychoanalytically about the reconstruction of knowledge is to think of it in terms of the subjective position in relation to castration and not only in terms of empirical data collected through the senses (Lajonquière pg. 195).

"The Alicia Case", reported by Lajonquière , exemplifies the issue of subjectivity acting directly on a subject's learning capacity.

"While treating herself for two years, one day Alicia discovered that 'the apparent can be misleading'. For her mother and for the school, she was silly and 'got stuck in this conviction', always repeating: 'I won't make it because I'm stupid'. At the age of ten, he still maintained a pre-logical thinking that prevented him from any operational learning (for example, mathematics). The therapist tried to 'attack' Alicia's certainty ('I'm silly'). And in one session, faced with the Piagetian test (term-to-term correlation) which consists of grouping identical amounts of white and black chips in different ways, she discovered the permanence of the quantity: 'This time Alicia did not adhere to the perceptible correspondence and

after a while time said: 'it seems that there are more black than white, but there are the same amount of white and black... it looks like something but it's not... maybe I look silly, but I'm not' (Baraldi apud Lajonquière , pg. 23/24).

Thus, the logical-mathematical concept of the permanence of quantity was affirmed, the gateway to formal logic, but another movement, an unconscious one, was also starting at this time, which would lead Alicia to all other pedagogical knowledge. Alicia was "shaken" in her conviction ("I'm silly"), enabling success in other learning processes, both because there was now a knowledge structure capable of processing them, and because Alicia was a subject capable of wanting to know. This can only happen when something in the unconscious has been shaken (Baraldi apud Lajonquière , 1993, p. 24).

For Lajonquière intelligence produces knowledge and desire produces knowledge. Together they form thought, "ancient product of reason". And the clash between these two Orders, or the conflict between intelligence and desire, causes error. Alicia's mistake is dismantled when "another paradoxical knowledge about herself" gives her the key to build knowledge beyond mere appearances. The unconscious ("desire paradox") inhibits equilibration; the error or fracture in learning is produced by the "clash between intelligence and desire". (pg. 104)

"It is not just a cognitive deficiency that makes it impossible to remove the error: what is fundamentally determinant is of the order of Freudian inhibition/castration" (p. 105).

"Alicia needs to rebuild a socially shared knowledge, such as elementary numerical conservation. Caught up in appearances, it confuses being and seeming: it confuses being silly and appearing silly. In the same way that it confuses the quantity of the tokens: as given to perception, their quantity seems different from that which is discovered through reason. The 'balance' that prevails in the cognitive circuit is not enough: Alicia always makes mistakes. And here is the limit of the epistemic subject, or of Piagetian psychology: it does not serve to address the subjective drama of the sub-

ject in this process of knowledge, which is the so-called 'affective'. As in Piaget the subject himself is not distinguished from his thinking (or, intelligence), equilibrium reigns absolute in all subjectivity, and not just in his knowledge (1993, Lajonquière , p.227).

Knowledge and intelligence are structured according to the logic of equilibrium, as Piaget wants. But desire and its subject are not established according to any progression or increasing equilibrium. Thus, according to Bacha, we are in the presence of two different orders: an "order of knowledge" and an "order of knowledge". The two orders are irreducible to each other, although they are subtly intertwined (1998, p. 111).

I approach here the theoretical proposition that defines the relationship between desire (knowledge) and knowledge as a relationship of determination of desire over knowledge. But what to think of the meaning that knowledge can have in the psychic wealth of a subject and that has been a great concern: the intellectuality provided by current formal schooling would only have a scientific sense (training intellectuals, scientists (and social (training citizens) as suggested by Neill's critique and by the experience of alternative schools? What relations would it have with the ends of education? Our assessment of the school and, simultaneously, of the teacher's identity depends on this. How does psychoanalysis respond to this interconnected set? allow us to go?

The paradox of knowledge can prevent the subject from recognizing the fundamental difference, which permeates his entire existence, between 'seeming' and 'being'.

"That was what happened to Alicia, who, trapped in emotional appearances (or, dare I say it, blinded by her unconscious), confused being and seeming. The progressivity of the Order of Knowledge was obstructed by the subject's unconscious subjective drama, which is not governed by any progression or growing balance, but by the paradox of knowledge. "Alicia is no longer adhered to the perceptive correspondence (the imaginary), when she starts to be able to distinguish 'being silly' from 'having the appearance

of being so'" (Lajonquière , 1993, p. 25).

Alicia, trapped in the imaginary (stuck in appearances), confused being and seeming, she was an empiricist and not a logician.

From a certain perspective, education is, for psychoanalysis, a means that society uses to adapt the subject to the social group. Freud said in one of his most notorious writings, " Three Essays on Sexuality " (1905), that education aims to teach children to control their impulses by "inhibiting, prohibiting and suppressing". He also stated that its essence was repression (1980, vol. VII, p.)

As the repression of impulses involves the risk of neurosis, this practice could be understood, from now on, as an enemy of psychoanalysis. From this point of view, the most important task of the educator would be the decision of how much, when and how to prohibit, in order to limit as much as possible the establishment of neurotic repressions that provoke excessive frustration, possibly traumatizing.

This formula may suggest an essential contradiction between the individual and social universes, in such a way that attending to one necessarily implies disregarding the other. Education would be the repression of impulses with individual harm for the benefit of society. This is Mannoni 's biggest criticism : "education would be an adaptation (repression) and this would define the disease" (1977, p. 44).

The limit of this adaptive conception of education was clearly evidenced by the schools, which oscillated between two extremes: now seeking to adapt the subject to society in what would be "traditional" education; sometimes in the more radical experiences of "alternative" schools (Bacha, 1998, p. 124).

Today, schools seem to be managing such polarization well. As for us, psychologists and teachers, involved with our training, we are faced with a theoretical requirement: we could see this polarization, and the impasses it gave rise to, as a sign of the insufficiency of this way of conceiving education. The definition of education as repression of instinctual life aiming at its adaptation to social reality should be reviewed, since it presupposes an essential an-

tagonism between individual and society, but how to affirm it absolutely if the human being survives because “the outside” comes to supply “the inside”?

We need to learn more about the inseparable bond between learning, playing and creating, rediscovering one of the most significant contributions of the analytical tradition to education: the denunciation of the antipathy between education and pleasure!!

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REPRESENTATIONS OF TEACHERS ON THE INCLUSION OF STUDENTS WITH ASPERGER SYNDROME: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Students with Asperger Syndrome (AS) represent important challenges in the educational process, so it is necessary to respond to current needs and promote the correct inclusion of this group in regular schools. Because it is understood that, in the urgency to include, the school often segregates these students for not understanding their learning needs and not understanding what the syndrome is. In this way, what motivated the choice of the theme “Teachers’ representations about the inclusion of students with Asperger’s Syndrome” was, exactly, to know the conceptions of a group of teachers about the inclusion of students with Asperger’s Syndrome and what are their experiences in relation to the theme, and from that, to be able to contribute to a better understanding of the Representations of teachers of the Municipal School X in Caldas Novas, Goiás. The methodology adopted was a qualitative approach with the application of a questionnaire to 05 teachers with the intention of knowing the representations they have about the inclusion of students with Asperger’s Syndrome. The study revealed that the teachers’ representation regarding the inclusion of students with AS was mostly positive and correlated with their attitudes toward students with this syndrome. In conclusion, although educational policies have addressed the access of students with AS, the results emphasize the fact that the teachers, and research subjects, still resist including these students completely.

Keywords: Asperger’s syndrome. Representations. Inclusion. Perceptions.

INTRODUCTION

Students with Asperger Syndrome (AS) represent important challenges in the educational process, so it is necessary to respond to current needs and promote the correct inclusion of this group in regular schools. Because it is understood that, in the urgency to include, the school often segregates these students for not understanding their learning needs and not understanding what the syndrome is.

In this way, what motivated the choice of the theme “Teachers’ representations about the inclusion of students with Asperger’s Syndrome” was, exactly, to know the conceptions of a group of teachers about the inclusion of students with Asperger’s Syndrome and what are their experiences in relation to the theme, and from that, to be able to contribute to a better understanding of the Representations of teachers of the Municipal School X in Caldas Novas - Goiás.

The prevalence of students with an autism spectrum disorder, especially Asperger’s Syndrome, increases every year in regular schools, and this reality has been a growing challenge for teachers in terms of providing these students with excellent educational opportunities in the classroom. regular (NOGUEIRA; BRASILEIRO, 2021).

The delimitation of this dissertation is in researching the representations of 05 (five) teachers at Municipal School X in Caldas Novas, Goiás, about the school inclusion of students with Asperger Syndrome. The field research took place from May 2019 to February 2020, with the approach research in social representation, and culminated in the use of 01 questionnaires with direct questions about the profile of the researched teachers and with open questions about the conceptions of representations on the inclusion of students with Asperger’s Syndrome in regular schools.

METHODOLOGY

Research with a qualitative approach, dynamics of Social Representation (SR). According to the structural approach, according to Campo-Redondo and Labarca (2009), an SR is organized into two systems: a central system and a peripheral system. To describe the structure of an SR, it is necessary

to identify its central core, that is, the primary organizer of the representation that gives meaning and value to the other elements (ABRIC, 2003).

The population consisted of teachers from the municipal school X in Caldas Novas, Goiás. From the indicated population, 05 teachers were selected who had students with Asperger’s Syndrome in their classes.

A web-based questionnaire was developed for the investigation based on previous studies on disability and on teachers’ attitudes toward the inclusion of students with Asperger’s Syndrome. It consisted of two association tasks and demographic data such as gender, age, level of education, length of service in education, and whether there had been a student with AS in the classroom.

The methods used to analyze the data obtained in this article fall under descriptive techniques. Two techniques specially developed for SR analysis were used as prototypical analyzes and similarity analyses. In addition, other more standardized statistical tools were used to analyze RS in Excel and SPSS Statistics software (Version 22).

RESULTS

First, analyses of the variables were carried out: sex, age, level of education, length of service in education, and whether there was already a student with AS in the classroom, the data were analyzed using Excel and SPSS Statistics software (Version 22), as recorded below:

Table 1 - Statistics

	Gender of participants	Age of participants	Participants’ education level	Length of service in Education	If you have had students with AS in the classroom
N Valid	5	5	5	5	5
Missing	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Author data (2021)

In this question, all subjects belong to the female gender.

They are between 23 and 50 years old, with 23 being the youngest and 50 being the oldest.

Table 2 - Age of participants

Valid	Frequency	Percentage	Valid percent	Cumulative percentage
23	1	20,0	20,0	20,0
25	1	20,0	20,0	40,0
42	1	20,0	20,0	60,0
48	1	20,0	20,0	80,0
50	1	20,0	20,0	100,0
Total	5	100,0	100,0	

Source: Author data (2021)

As for the level of education, 2 teachers have only a degree in Pedagogy, 2 have a specialization in Special and Inclusive Education and Libras and 1 (one) has a PhD.

Table 3 - Participants' education level

Valid	Frequency	Percentage	Valid percent	Cumulative percentage
Degree in Pedagogy	2	40,0	40,0	40,0
Specialization	2	40,0	40,0	80,0
PhD degree	1	20,0	20,0	100,0
Total	5	100,0	100,0	

Source: Author data (2021)

The length of service was also questioned in which 1 (one) teacher has only 1 (one) year of service in education, 1 has 2 years, 1 has 6 years, 1 has 8 years and 1 has 27 years. It is visible the distance of time of service between the teachers and that only 2 have less than 3 years in education.

Table 4 - Length of service in Education

Valid	Frequency	Percentage	Valid percent	Cumulative percentage
1	1	20,0	20,0	20,0
2	1	20,0	20,0	40,0
6	1	20,0	20,0	60,0
8	1	20,0	20,0	80,0
27	1	20,0	20,0	100,0
Total	5	100,0	100,0	

Source: Author data (2021)

The answer to this was unanimous, all the teachers had or have students with AS in the classroom.

Table 5 - If there were students with AS in the classroom.

Valid	Frequency	Percentage	Valid percent	Cumulative percentage
Yes	5	100,0	100,0	100,0

Source: Author data (2021)

Categorization was conducted in several steps. The first step used a qualitative approach to explore and categorize the free associations provided by the participants. Phrases that expressed the same semantic content but differed in form, eg singular/plural, were grouped together.

Synonyms and semantically equivalent phrases were placed in the same category, for example, the category called lack of executive functions contained words or phrases such as lack of impulse control, difficulty initiating and completing tasks, lack of focus, and lack of logical thinking. The categories were based on 1 study by Paganotti and Osti (2020). This was done to reduce the number of categories that would gradually emerge into broader categories.

Example of the different steps:

- a) Acceptance of differences by students;
- b) Tolerance;
- c) Peer interaction;
- d) Understanding of colleagues;
- e) Patience of colleagues and employees;
- f) Comprehension;
- g) Environmental understanding.

When there was a classification discrepancy, the item was analyzed. In this way, we arrived at the result regarding the classification of phrases. However, three associations (what, how and need) for students with AS and ten for inclusion. The evocations (motive, needs (2), individualism, presence, rhythm, (3)) were left uncategorized and omitted in further analyses.

In step two, the valency of the given word/phrase was identified and used for categorization. This sometimes produced dichotomous categories. A term with a negative value within the same

category sometimes creates a category of its own, for example, items with a negative charge in the structure and routine category form the category need for structure and routine. The categories that emerged underwent additional analysis.

As the sample was collected in only 1 (one) municipal school and with 05 teachers who had or have students with AS, the results of the studies may not be generalized to all teachers. Our aim, however, was to provide an in-depth understanding of teachers' SRs regarding the inclusion of children with AS in mainstream classes.

In general, differences in results are relatively small and, consequently, care must be taken in drawing conclusions. However, as the research participants share the same social and professional context that also shapes their SR, large differences are excluded. However, the structure of the SRs indicated consistent similarities and differences based on previous experience and how these contributed to forming the SRs.

In addition, as the surveys were conducted through an access link, the researcher did not have information about the teachers who did not respond to the survey. This information can improve the interpretation of the findings. Inclusion is a culturally specific concept that we assume reduces misunderstandings in the current context in which inclusive education policies are formulated.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this article have several important implications for increasing the achievement of educational goals and reducing school absenteeism among students with AS.

The results suggest that careful work is needed before welcoming students diagnosed with AS into school. The beliefs of the responding teachers and their practices do not coincide with the objectives of full inclusion.

There is a need for educational programs to better prepare and equip teachers for the challenge of including students with AS in the regular classroom. Third, the idea of inclusion may need a general adjustment. Although teachers are generally favorable to students diagnosed with AS, their SR

also indicates some reluctance. Representations need to be studied in more detail to be better understood. However, they also suggest that the idea of inclusion, however politically correct it may be, may lack full contact with the day-to-day reality of the classroom.

Although slowly, changes are taking place, newly qualified teachers are more apt to adapt to the school environment.

The results indicate that various professionals need to engage in collaborative professional development. They still indicate that they were like previous studies, which showed that the whole school lacks a common goal of inclusion or what seems to be the current state in which different employees provide support according to their particular function.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CHILD'S CONTACT WITH THE NATURE THESE DAYS

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THE PENCIL

Manoel de Barros

The nature of God is too great.
I wanted to make myself a little nature particular.
So small that it could fit on the tip of my pencil.
If it were her, I wish, just the size of my backyard.
just one tamarin tree was going to grow for use by birds.
And let the mornings prepare other birds to compose the blue of the sky.
And if it wasn't too much to ask, I would like at the bottom flowed a river.
The most important thing
What I wanted was the river.
In the river, me and our group, I would all go day to play cangapé in running waters.
That, I think, would be my little nature particular:
As far as my little pencil could reach.

INTRODUCTION

The future has arrived and with it many questions that not even the most fertile imagination would have been able to imagine a few years ago. The world has changed, and that includes entertainment, routine, machines... life! Today, technology undoubtedly allows us to do a lot of interesting things. We can maintain daily contact with distant relatives, meet old friends, and go shopping without leaving home, among thousands of other wonders. But how to evolve without creating a distance from the benefits of the primitive?

“Gathering the clay from our humus to remake humanity in us by hand. “
(Piorsky)

Today we live in a culture that values the sense of sight too much, to the point of ignoring others. We don't have time to stop to smell the smells of life, we don't pay attention to small sounds and even less let our skin feel different textures that are everywhere. But what do we see if we no longer allow ourselves to even observe the moments where memories are created naturally because we want to photograph everything at all times?

Our children, from a very young age, are already spectators of ready-made elements. They do not need to create and are not challenged to travel with their ideas, as they are born being bombarded by a series of technological contents. An excess of colors, music, and, mainly, commercial appeal.

Thus, more and more, the little ones are breaking the cycles of relationships and many have come to think that food comes from the market, that milk comes from the carton, and that certain animals, such as sheep, do not even exist in real life. We are increasingly creating consumers and not citizens! We deal with a generation that finds it difficult to have fun and that always needs to bring something along to entertain itself, which can be an electronic device or even anti-stress toys. Very young people, but who from an early age already carry health problems, such as obesity, anxiety, and insomnia. They are children raised indoors, often small, and who, even when they have the chance to be outdoors, are in cars or strollers.

“Science can classify and name the organs of a

thrush,

but cannot measure its charms.

Science cannot calculate how many horses' strength exists in the song of a thrush. Anyone who accumulates too much information loses the ability to guess: divine The thrushes divine.”
(Manoel de Barros)

The problem is real and far more serious than most want to accept. The sooner the change begins, the better for everyone. But where to start? Perhaps the simplest answer is all around us, in our history and our ancestral memories. What the modern, scientific, and commercial world may only consider “child's play”, “playing in the dirt” or even “mess”, maybe the key for us to return to having more active, healthy children and nourishing their imaginations.

“Contact with nature improves all the most important milestones of a healthy childhood – immunity, memory, sleep, learning capacity, sociability, physical capacity – and has significantly contributed to the overall well-being of children and young people. The evidence points out that the benefits are mutual: just as children and adolescents need nature, nature needs children and young people.” (Children and Nature Program and Brazilian Society of Pediatrics, 2019)”

There is still a long way to go for nature to regain the place it has lost in the lives of young people over generations, but some families, schools, and professionals are taking their role seriously and it is already possible to see the results. The following work aims to show how important nature is to people's lives in general, but especially to children. Aiming to relate information from a vast bibliography, courses, and the daily observation of children from two classes of 1st year of Elementary School, within the Escola Vira-Virou, in Rio de Janeiro, where children are encouraged to explore and interact with the environment daily. The observations and interviews were carried out in a wide space, with a dirt floor, some fruit trees, and a small tree house made entirely of wood. This school space is called “Orchard” and even though it is just one of the places for free activities and games that the school has, it is, by far, the preferred one by the vast majority of children.

HOW CAN CONTACT WITH NATURE BENEFIT CHILDREN?

According to Vygotsky (1989), we consider that children constitute themselves in culture and are producers of culture. However, we understand that humans are, simultaneously, beings of culture and beings of nature. Its development takes place in the interaction with members of a species that has historical, cultural, rational, linguistic, and political specificity (LOUREIRO, 2006; GUIMARÃES, 2006). Thus, children are beings who are constituted in connection with other beings, human and non-human and are empowered in this state of connection (ESPINOSA, 1983).

According to Chauí (2001, pg. 209), “nature is the active principle that animates and moves beings, a spontaneous force capable of generating and caring for all beings created and moved by it. (...) the substance of beings. It throbs within every human being as an intimate feeling of life”. It is the substance present in all things and beings that make up the cosmos. From this perspective, human beings are part of nature. As in the philosophy of the pre-Socratics (Bornheim, 2001), Nature is life itself, in its physical-affective manifestations. We go through many changes, but biologically we are the same creatures.

Thus, all the vain effort that human beings make to distance themselves from their origins, innate affinities, or being superior to nature, is initially ignored by children. They appreciate the land, the water, and especially the mixture of these: the mud! They show an intimacy with these elements, which we have already lost, due to lack of habit, time, or having been pruned when we were younger. Even though it has not yet been scientifically used,

the term “Nature Deficit Disorder” created by LOUV (2008) has a clear and frightening concept of what the absence of contact with nature can bring negatively to human life, especially during childhood, such as decreased use of the senses, difficulty concentrating, and higher rates of physical and emotional illness.

By playing with what the earth gives us, the child is creating a bond with nature, its roots, and its ancestors. The toy made by her with natural materials allows her ability to create to be discovered and explored. Gradually, he remodels the world with everything he imagines. Children’s imagination needs to be nurtured to expand and when there are no stimuli it is atrophied. For Bachelard (1991), “the imagination is a fourth kingdom of nature, where the universe of inhabiting, fitting in and resignifying exists”.

Vygotsky (1998) also highlights the role of the act of playing in the construction of children’s thinking, as it is by playing that child reveal their cognitive, visual, auditory, tactile, and motor states, their way of learning and entering into a cognitive relationship. with the world of events, people, things and symbols.

“The materiality of playing, when it consists of unscientific material substances, decomposed, dismantled by time or coming from nature, has the power to unframe the imagination. It allows the child to create with greater freedom his experience.”
(PIORSKY, 2016)

The hallmarks of a healthy childhood - immunity, memory, learning ability, sociability, and physical disposition - are supported by contact with the natural environment. Research by the Criança e Natureza Program, the Alana Institute, and the Brazilian Society of Pediatrics, also points out that these benefits are mutual because just as children need nature, nature needs them.

The interaction with natural materials also works to sharpen the senses and raise awareness of the child’s body. Through sounds, the child gets closer to the nature of things (wood, iron, glass...) and becomes more and more awake to perceive the details of the world. As for the smell, real odors (even the most fetid ones) help us discover the identity of things.

Free play is not encouraged as it is not profitable for anyone. Increasingly stringent restrictions, the excessive development of cities, condominium rules, and necessary environmental regulations are showing, without noticing, that free play is not a good option. But it is not news to many that outdoor activities or other types of contact with natural elements bring health benefits. In the 1970s, land activities were already used to treat the mentally ill and before that, in the 1950s, gardening began to be used as therapy. Currently, zootherapy has already had its effectiveness proven, with pets helping their owners to control high blood pressure. But unfortunately, the use of nature as an additional or preventive alternative therapy, especially with children, is still being ignored.

“Contact with nature influences the way children learn. Learning in a natural context allows direct experiences with the subject, making it more interesting and easier to understand.” (Moss 2012, Erikson and Ernest 2011).

It is a fact that the natural open environment is the main source of sensory stimulation that a child can have. It encourages fantasy, and make-believe and enables choices for creative engagement. The child can learn things long before they are subject in school. This is made clear in the following dialog: When observing the children in the “orchard”, a first-year student who is usually extremely agitated, has been reflecting for many minutes in front of a large puddle of mud. So he talks to the teacher who doesn't know if stepping into the puddle will cover his foot.

The teacher says:

- Is this puddle too deep?

And he, visibly intrigued, replies:

-I don't know how to measure!

The teacher trying to instigate him asks:

-How do you think we can measure things?

- I think I'll use my hand!

And so he did, placing his hand sideways in the center of the muddy water, which covered all his fingers. But still not satisfied:

-I don't know if the big puddle is all the same “size”.

- And what can we use to measure?

He was thoughtful because he did not imagine that he was allowed to put any measuring instrument in the water. So, the teacher suggested that the boy

take a ruler to measure the height of all the points in the puddle. At that moment his eyes shone with joy! And the person in charge even gave him a challenge to choose one of the two rulers, the big one or the little one, that was on his table. The boy, who has several socio-affective issues and is constantly in need of help to maintain control of his body and his actions, spent several minutes having fun in the orchard, getting to know different depths, testing his limits, and creating new hypotheses and knowledge. At that moment, he became the center of attention of a group that was previously engaged in another game but loved the idea of seeing him measuring the depth of the puddle.

“Reality is what is happening out there, not what is happening in your mind or on your computer screen.”

(Paul Dayton, Marine ecologist)

In the space of natural playing, leadership is often given by creativity or other criteria, which are not physical. This creates the opportunity for different children to exercise leadership and manage to show their ideas and personality, removing the focus that was often on who was the best at sports or the most resourceful or extroverted.

Naturalistic intelligence needs to be valued, developed and appreciated like others. Typical of those who have a strong connection with nature and an unusual ability to identify and distinguish animals, plants, climate formations, and other elements of the natural world. At school, they have more facilities in Biology and Geography.

Many see technology as the salvation of the world and believe that only through it will we be able to evolve or reach success. They do not see the harmful effects of screens, but they are afraid of nature and end up passing on excessive fears to their children. Of course, it's understandable that the sharp rise in violence is causing adults to rethink where they should take their children. However, research on the benefits of nature should also be taken into account at this time. According to Louv, studies suggest that exposure to nature reduces symptoms of ADHD, and improves resistance to stress, depression, and also cognitive skills.

Playing in an open environment children learn about the world, even about caring for and

preserving their environments. A place like this also stimulates more vibrant social and neighborhood relationships, as they can become spaces for living together, leisure, and games, providing fun moments in groups.

The elements of nature can help children develop a sense of self-regulation and risk management, which builds autonomy and responsibility. Adults can observe, but without intervening directly, so that they discover the real risks of their attitudes, challenge themselves and increase their self-esteem. A wide and natural space serves as an invitation to practice physical activity, helping to combat obesity and other problems very common in modern children.

But it is important to emphasize that for children any nature is enough! Backyard space makes no difference and often a backyard game becomes more interesting than a mountain expedition.

“I think the backyard where we played is bigger than the city. We only discover this after we grow up. We discover that the size of things has to be measured by the intimacy we have with things. It has to be like it happens with love. Thus, the pebbles in our backyard are always bigger than the other stones in the world. Precisely for the reason of intimacy (...)” (Manoel de Barros)

NATURE IN SCHOOLS

If experts are making an effort every day to show the benefits of growing up in contact with nature, the little ones love being outdoors so much, and today the school occupies a large space in the lives of children, what would be the responsibility of this institution and their educators, in distancing the little ones from the natural environment?

According to BNCC, the Natural Sciences area aims to promote scientific literacy, so that students understand and interpret the natural world and can transform it. To do so, they need to get in touch with nature and reconnect with it, through theory and practice, used as a pedagogical tool to work on different skills. By exploring nature and its different elements, in the most varied situations, the child is discovering and apprehending the world, essential since kindergarten.

But the reality is far from that. When visiting most schools, we still found cold environments, a lot of plastic, and an empty and lifeless spaces. These environments, despite all the evolution in the world, are stuck in the past. They are places where there is no time or space to live and be happy because the “priorities” are different. Concern for the future, anxiety, and lack of habit make parents (and consequently some children) think that playing is a waste of time.

Normally, those responsible believe that sports or Physical Education classes are equivalent to playing time, but this is not true! The idea is to have moments reserved for playing without structure and adult intervention so that the experience is valid and complete. Planned activities, even outdoors, are generally weaker in long-term memory than spontaneous experiences.

Unfortunately, it is still rare for people to see the potential and importance of life in childhood. For many years, children’s lives were not taken into account and their wishes and needs were never heard. Schooling was intended to indoctrinate ideologies and the accumulation of goods and information. The intention was only to reproduce what was being done and being different was not an option.

In the past, children were less aware of what happens to the planet, but they used the outdoor spaces much more for leisure activities. One explanation for this is that any kind of problem was not “children’s business” and it was not common for adults to spend their time trying to explain what was happening with nature or about many other subjects. Another is that people lived many decades alienated, believing and acting as if everything that nature gives us is eternal.

Contact with nature needs to be part of school activities so that children understand its importance and are engaged with environmental preservation. It is also the responsibility of schools to help young people become a generation that will find solutions to the crises that humanity faces today. It will be up to them to seek to control pollution, manage non-renewable resources, use energy better, conserve the soil, protect biological diversity, and reduce waste production, among many other problems that they will inherit.

For this, it is necessary to teach them sustainable practices in the use of natural resources, based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) proposed by the UN. The SDGs propose global actions so that by 2030 we have better living conditions on the planet, based on sustainability, according to the 15th objective: “Terrestrial Life”. “Protect, restore and promote the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss”.

According to child and nature expert Chawla, “The positive effects of developing with nature on health, concentration, creative play and bonding with the natural world can form the basis for developing an environmental awareness.”

If children are not attached to nature and everything that is part of it, they will not reap the benefits of that contact and will not feel committed to taking care of it. It’s a cycle! It is necessary to have a link, a relationship of belonging so that they feel responsible for the care, from the most basic. The contact with nature allows the biopsychosocial development of the child, which establishes a healthy interaction between him and the environment in which he lives, which includes the environment as an integral part of the social, psychological, and biological aspects of the individual.

Still according to Chawla, if the child has the habit of playing freely in a natural space until the age of 11, he will probably become a person more concerned with the environment in the future. She also uses the term “contagious caring attitude”, referring to an adult who has a good attitude toward the environment and becomes a reference for children. The crisis in ecology is rooted in the way we educate future generations. Today, education often ends up alienating life to emphasize what will bring future success and financial return.

Walks, even if sporadic and to nearby places, connect students to the surroundings and initiate the “belonging process” to the space. Vegetable gardens, butterfly gardens, land spaces, and lawns are simple examples that can make the school space more attractive. A visionary school management or a conscientious teacher can be the catalyst for the beginning of an important process of change.

“All places are places to learn. Forests, backyards, and territories are to be investigated, with trees, rivers, clearings, squares, and beaches. nature is a wealth of possibilities for aesthetic education, not only for children, as for all human beings.” (BARBIERI, 2012, p.115).

During a conversation with a student who played in the “Pomar,” I asked:

- What do you like to do most here at school?

He, without hesitating for a second, replied:

- Play in the orchard!

Unsurprisingly, I wanted to find out more:

- But what do you like to do here?

- I like to play after the rain, when there’s mud and everything looks like poop. It’s cool to jump in and watch the mud rise!

Still wanting to challenge him, I asked:

-But when it’s dry you don’t like to come here, right? No puddles at all!

-I like it! I like to run around and play with the gemstones when it’s dry.

- What stones are those?

- The round ones I use to make necklaces or the ones that look like I caught them on the moon. – he replied, showing me some small seeds and some grains of earth.

-Do you like to do anything else here in the orchard?

-All! Once we even heard a story here!

Generally, children are confined for most of the school period, as if reality were reduced to the internal spaces of classrooms, and they were born for school, not for the world. According to Tibira (2006), there are two main reasons why children are imprisoned: “The ideology of the built space” and the “Culture of cleanliness” and both are very common in schools today. The first consists of occupying all spaces on the land with the construction of rooms, doing away with all the green areas and external spaces that could be used by children for various activities, and prioritizing closed spaces. The second and no less serious or important issue is what she called “Cleaning culture”, which talks about children not being able to get dirty, as they need to be handed over to those responsible exactly the way they arrived at school.

THERE IS STILL HOPE

“Currently, the greatest modernity is to return to essences.”

(Lea Tiriba, Environmental educator and teacher)

Humans are losing their ability to experience the world directly. Internet addiction is already a reality and some studies relate the highest rate of depression to those who access the network more. This panorama occurs due to the accelerated growth of Internet access and new technologies, naturally leading to a greater sedentary lifestyle and emotional seclusion.

“On the horizon of the set of reasons and questions presented about the situation of children being confined, one conclusion is that being outdoors is not a definition, a pedagogical imperative, but an option for each individual.

school, teachers or adults responsible for the children.”

(Tiriba, 2006)

What we often find in schools are tight and inadequate spaces. The most important thing for many is that they have chairs, tables, and a board to show the syllabus. It would be incredible if every school presented architecture that contemplated the body, sun, greenery, and trees, but this is far from reality. One possible option is to visit nearby places and use every possible space in the school: a small garden has great potential! And also bringing nature into the children’s daily lives in another way: offering earth, water, stones, seeds, and clay, preparing an environment with natural artifices. In this way, nature becomes not something distant. It comes into existence and this tactile experience, of smell, of color, materializes. This makes it much easier to start connecting with her.

“Among the schools in our network, one of the ones with the smallest patio is one of the ones with the greatest diversity of possibilities for children, with a variety of trees, a compost garden, and different areas for playing. Materializing a courtyard proposal is much more in the design than in the financial resource”

(Rita Moraes, Pedagogical Adviser for Early Childhood Education at the Novo Hamburgo Municipal Department of Education)

To improve future generations, it is necessary to have a broader vision and change, even if small, now so that the results come in the long term. The reality today is still that we rarely find bare feet, we see nature being used only as decoration, and contact with water is made only for hygiene. It is difficult to teach them to enjoy the good that nature does and to respect it without having contact with it. This role of presenting the natural environment to the child belongs to the family and can also be performed by the school.

According to Robin Moore, a university professor, children live by the senses whose experiences connect the outside world to the inside. The natural environment is the main source of sensory stimulation and the freedom to play and explore is essential for healthy development.

It was enchanting to observe the Pomar’s moments carefully for weeks and to observe the real power of nature. Understanding how agitated children can calm down using only earth, how introverted children manage to lead games, even for a few minutes, and realize the joy of the little ones every day when after lunch we said: “You can go to the orchard!” For many long minutes, I compared those moments with those I experienced in my childhood, in a good school with great natural potential, but which was never used! Would I have more running skills if my school looked like this? Would I be less afraid of bugs? Would I be less ashamed to expose myself in certain games? Doubts permeate the mind!

The observations make clear the child’s need for space and how this space makes their ideas flow. I saw tree leaves turn into dolls, children turn into

jaguars and walk on 4 “paws” and the land turns into food. I was able to observe the sale of stones and coffee made from muddy water by girls who, at the age of 6, say they have cell phones and dance apps. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that Piorsky talks about toys extracted from nature going beyond the issue of consumption, as there is something immaterial of unique importance in them. This was also clear when we made dolls using green mango and sticks. At that moment, I’m proud to have been the adult who made the difference, because they wanted dolls and didn’t know how to make them. I gave the idea of using the green mangoes that fell still small, as some tribes still do today, and quickly each child appeared proudly displaying their “son” made of fruit and sticks.

Therefore, I conclude that healing the lost bond is not impossible but quite necessary. To improve future generations it is necessary to have a broader vision and that changes are made now so that the results come in the long term. We can already see that in some places changes are starting to take shape, as they have already begun to realize that physical and mental health depends on the environment.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICE IN MEDIATING THE SKILLS AND POTENTIALITIES OF STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Special Education has changed over the years. There was a belief that a person with a disability should not be included in the social environment because they are incapable. Today, it is understood the need for inclusion to facilitate the development of that person, as well as provide means of greater interaction between people. but the teacher is not always ready to deal with this student with a disability. When we talk about teacher training, we must take into account factors such as availability of time, area of expertise, and professional development, among others. For better professional training it is necessary to develop work in consonance with cognitive and socio-emotional skills, aiming at a better performance with the student and consequently better teaching and learning. The activities should be concentrated on the higher forms of cognitive work: creating, applying, analyzing, and evaluating, with the support of their peers and teachers. In summary, means moving events that were traditionally done in class out of the room classroom, according to Lage Platt and Treglia (2000). Technologies have certainly helped education professionals to provide resources that help the process of learning and it is up to the educator to apply these resources in the best way, to promote the learning and intellectual evolution of these students.

KEYWORDS: Specialized Educational Service. Inclusion. Teaching. Teaching Practice

INTRODUCTION

This article demonstrates how working with Inclusion is not an easy task, it takes a lot of dedication. The Professor of Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE) performs meticulous work that is completely individualized, from plans, interviews, reports, case studies, evaluation, and adaptation of activities.

The AEE teacher must develop a work that encompasses all instances of the school, the management and pedagogical team, the teachers in the common room, the family, and especially the students in the regular room with the students served in the School Units. If there weren't so many existing difficulties with Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE), we are currently facing a health crisis. And now how to get the job done? Will we be able to have a positive result?

In this sense, the SEA teacher's main objective is to develop stimuli in students that are indispensable for full development, through pedagogical, technological, and educational resources, contributing significantly to independence and autonomy. To do so, it is necessary to have qualifications in Pedagogy or a degree in non-critical areas in the municipality; the priority is to be an effective servant of SEDUC, who has completed a postgraduate course in the field of Special Education. Know the national guidelines of the Special Education Policy and the guidelines issued by the Superintendence of Modalities and Themes; special needs/Special Education Management; • act in line with the other Programs of the Regional Coordination of Education, under the coordination of the Pedagogical Advisory of the Regional Coordination, via Inclusion Mediator; work in the Multifunctional Resource Rooms - and in the Specialized Educational Service Rooms - AEE, complementing and supplementing the pedagogical action carried out in the common classroom, with students with disabilities, autism spectrum disorders/ASD and high abilities/giftedness; subsidize the pedagogical activities of the educational units based on continuing education activities, guiding the Regent Teachers with regard to the teaching-learning process of students with disabilities, global developmental disorders, high abilities/giftedness; articulate actions with the pedagogical coordination,

involving the Regent Teacher and the Pedagogical Support Professional, for the implementation of an inclusive formal educational practice, making the curriculum more flexible and developing evaluation processes that consider the levels of development and the cognitive and socio-affective areas of the development; guide, support and collaborate with the preparation of the Student Learning/Development Report, bimonthly and annually, for students with Intellectual Disability and/or TGD/ASD to participate in meetings, meetings, seminars, courses and other actions promoted by SEDUC / SMTE/GEE/CRE; participate in the elaboration of the educational unit's internal regulations, as well as the Pedagogical Political Project, providing guidance on the institutionalization of the AEE offer and on the pedagogical action of inclusive education; subsidize and guide Regent Teachers, Pedagogical Support Professionals, Libras Interpreters, with regard to the specificities of students with disabilities, global developmental disorders/autistic spectrum disorder, high skills/giftedness .

Education is the way of building knowledge and necessary actions to integrate human beings into society. This concept is divided into two moments: informal education, received in the family core, and erudite, or formal, education received through academies. Throughout history, we realize that the educational process has been a need sought by man. In rock art, there were already indications of attempts at education in a more formal sense, even with the objective of survival.

In the West, Greek antiquity allowed its citizens to deepen their knowledge through academies. Plato had his school, although in a different way than what we understand today as an academic school environment. However, it was in Greece the beginning of studies and the creation of sciences through philosophy.

However, inclusive education is something new in the history of Brazil. It is known that the first special school was created at the time of D. Pedro II – the emperor who was a great lover of knowledge – in the 50s of the 19th century. The school served deaf-mute and visually impaired students. However, at that time there was great prejudice against people who had disabilities, leaving them on the margins of society and denying them contact with people

considered “normal”.

In the 1920s and 1930s, with the Escola Nova, people with disabilities were understood as cases of medical pathology. New School teachers, however, introduced education-oriented psychology studies and education-oriented intelligence tests, which classified or excluded students who were considered intellectually retarded.

Subsequently, the Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB nº 4024/61) provided for the integration of special students, at that time called exceptional, in the general education system and financial support from the government to the private sector that was willing to offer education for the specials. Around 1969, 80% of special education institutions were private, thus excluding low-income people, in addition to the separation between the “exceptional” and the “normal”.

Only with the CF of 1988 and the new LDB of 1996 did the school reach the milestone of inclusive education. In item III of article 208 of the CF, it establishes that the State must guarantee specialized assistance to people with disabilities, preferably in the regular education network. The Law of Guidelines and Bases of Education of 1996, in item III of article 4, establishes free specialized assistance to students with special needs, preferably in the regular education network.

With the Salamanca Declaration of 1994, it is established that those with special educational needs must have access to regular schools, which must accommodate them within a child-centered pedagogy.

Despite so many advances in the legal field, guaranteeing rights to people with disabilities, the school and teacher training courses still have certain deficiencies. The school environment has been changing and, little by little is becoming more inclusive. As for teacher training courses, there is still only general information about special education, and special education teachers need to seek additional training to better serve their students.

Assistive Technology is still a new term, used to identify the entire arsenal of Resources and Services that contribute to providing or expanding

the functional abilities of people with disabilities and consequently promoting independent living and inclusion. It is also defined as “a wide range of equipment, services, strategies and practices designed and applied to alleviate problems encountered by individuals with disabilities” (Cook and Hussey • Assistive Technologies: Principles and Practices • Mosby – Year Book, Inc., 1995). The concept in Brazil, by the Technical Assistance Committee - CAT, instituted by ORDINANCE No. 142, OF NOVEMBER 16, 2006 proposes.

Assistive Technology is an area of knowledge, with an interdisciplinary characteristic, which encompasses products, resources, methodologies, strategies, practices, and services that aim to promote functionality, related to the activity and participation of people with disabilities, disabilities or reduced mobility, aiming at their autonomy, independence, quality of life and social inclusion.

JUSTIFICATION

As neither all you students have accessed The computers It is cell phones, it was necessary to resort to the relatives creating one group with your students It is to work with the per video calls It is Shipping activities ‘via WhatsApp of parents and O teacher himself made an appointment individual for to help O student to answer online.

It is important to insert the context in which I, the researcher, am being inserted. I started working in education in 1994, when I passed a public in the city of Morrinhos, State of Goiás. I worked at State School Alfredo Nasser, the first Reference School for Inclusion in Morrinhos to receive special students as a literacy teacher and also as a facilitator of the Laboratory in Computing Educational (LIE) It is a coordinator Pedagogical.

Inclusion, in fact, only happens when there are responses to differences. so the schools must adopt practices pedagogical that enable people with disabilities to meaningful learning, which recognizes and value the knowledge that they are capable in to produce, observing O your rhythm It is your possibilities. One aspect relevant is O’s knowledge of theoretical specificities surrounding autism disability.

According to the Law of Guidelines and Base of

National Education - LDBEN n.9.394/96, public students of special education are considered those with special needs resulting from innate or acquired factors, of a temporary or permanent nature, that is, those who present: Physical Disability, Hearing Impairment, Deafness, Visual Impairment, Disability Intellectual Disability, Multiple Disability, Deafblindness, Global Developmental Disorders – PDD, High abilities/giftedness.

Thus, to discuss the importance of service education effective I propose to discuss some aspects that we deem important for The effectiveness of the inclusion full of teaching with autism It is a deficiency of intellectual at Network Regular of Teaching. In agreement with good (1999):

“Within the current conditions of Brazilian education, there is no way to include children with needs educational special at the teaching regular without support skilled, what offer to the teachers of these classes, guidance It is assistance”.

Thus, inclusive education offers adequate teaching to differences to the needs of each student and should not be seen from the side or in isolation, but as part of the regular system. Therefore, the essential question for the effectiveness of this concept is whether The training proper is to be continued for teachers (SANT’ANA, 2005; GLAT & FERNANDES, 2005).

You challenges faced for the educator front The policy in education inclusive levels expressive when it treats the inclusion of students with pervasive expressive disorders in development. These challenges present themselves as a result of the reduced training professional referent The portion component of needs educational specials. Teacher training is an aspect that deserves emphasis when addressing inclusion. Many prospective teachers feel insecure and anxious before the possibility of receiving a child.

There is a general complaint from students of pedagogy, degree, and teachers: “No I went prepared to lead with children with deficiency” (LIME, 2002, p.40).

Teacher training is indeed a necessity, becoming essential, however, we have to take into account urgently that such professionals must have

conditions for what these qualifications be effected It is what not stay only in plans. Then The majority of our professionals from the areas of educational work in two The three shifts, that pilgrimage in between shifts It is until same schools, make it difficult It is become impracticable The your participation in the qualifications offered, whether online, in person or hybrid with special needs in the room of class.

Educating a person with Pervasive Developmental Disorder is an experience that leads educators to review and question their conceptions about development, education, normality, and professional competence. this relationship put proof of the skills of educators. As to help those students The approach whether in way of meanings and significant human relationships. what means we can employ to help them communicate, to attract your attention It is interesting in the world? No, we have answers ready, however, we intend to offer the opportunity to reflect together on that theme so we find possible ways.

Any approach about O topic he must reference your pioneer Leo Kanner It is Hans Asperger who, separately, published your first works about those disorders. Kanner, in 1943, described The condition of eleven children considered special, with characteristics different from a concept that was very much in vogue in the era, schizophrenia childish.

Per one far away time, to the researches It studies about of theme they were guided for the conception from the psychomotricity, this It is, you Disorders global they were Classified us groups of psychoses. These theories were overcome It is today it is described that autism is linked to genetic causes and associated with causes environmental. From the 1980s onwards, the conceptions that perceive the Disorders Global/Invasive as disobey behavioral. faction (2005, P. 19) define what:

People with Pervasive Developmental Disorders (PDD) have, and common severe and invasive damage in the various areas of development, (skills in intervention Social reciprocal, in communication or presence in behaviors and/or interests stereotyped – activities It is movements I repeated you) It is each one differs from other

through of some characteristics individualized. (...)

Still for this author, there are five subtypes of PDD: Autistic Disorder, Rett's, Asperger's, Childhood Disintegration (PDD), and Pervasive Disorder Development without other Specification (TID-SOE). Students with Disorders global of Development are those that present one frame in alteration at the development neuro psychomotor, commitment in the relations social, at communication or motor stereotypies.

In that specter, the MEC defines what O Service Educational Specialized - AEE, whose function is to identify, develop and organize pedagogical and educational resources accessible to eliminate the barriers to The full participation of the students, considering your specific needs. This service complements and/or supplements the training of the students with views The autonomy It is independence at school and out of it.

Special education services and resources are those who ensure conditions in access to the curriculum per quite from the promotion from the accessibility of teaching materials, spaces, and equipment, to communication systems It is information and to the set of activities in school.

We start from the premise that teachers, in their initial training, are not prepared to work in a classroom with students with special needs educational specials. Like this, our search to understand O paper of specialized educational service, after specific training to work in the rooms of support and the use of assistive technologies.

For so much O goal in our search It is to analyze The importance of specialized educational service, discussing the implications of techniques in the process of mediation of skills It is the potentialities of the students with deficiency.

The steps of this research were guided by the specific objectives: a) to list the several learning tools and their uses used in the community school; b) list arguments in favor of the use of assistive technologies in the process education of students with disabilities; c) identify the aspects that facilitate and/or hinder the learning process of special students. d) Identify the use of assistive technologies as a tool facilitator in teaching

learning to students with deficiencies. It is) Identity to the difficulties that you teachers face It is resisted to the use of technologies assistive.

Know The reality of research already developed about The theme allowed us to see with bigger clarity The reality about The which we were researching, we delimited our research strategy with the definition of the type of search It is we opted for per one search qualitative.

When we work with observation, and interacting with your subjects It is with The reality in search, that methodology Show yourself most suitable because it allows the researcher one bigger flexibility in data collection and analysis.

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH CONTEXT

In the research, an investigation was carried out at the CEPI Alfredo Nasser State School, located on Avenida Prefeito Manoel Lemos de Mendonça s/nº Setor Oeste, Morrinhos – GO.

The institution's management team, consisting of a director and a pedagogical coordinator, provided free access for all research to be carried out.

RESEACH FOCUS

We opted for the qualitative methodology in which we developed the search for data in the field research. Experiencing reality allowing to observe it closely allows the researcher to develop a critical sense based on the theoretical perspective that underlies the look of the research.

The research has an exploratory character and the researcher, according to Rodrigo (2008), has the power not only to describe the situation without intervention but is also capable of having a great analytical range and questioning and confronting different situations, as well as generating new ones. theories and questions for future investigations.

Such characteristics overlap with the general characteristics of qualitative research. It can therefore be said that the approach is qualitative. This investigation is understood as one in which:

[...] the scientist is at the same time the subject and

the object of his research. Research development is unpredictable. The researcher's knowledge is partial and limited. The purpose of the sample is to produce in-depth and illustrative information: whether it is small or large, what matters is that it is capable of producing new information. (DESLAURIERS, 1991, apud. SILVEIRA AND GERHARDT, 2009.P.32).

This is a useful method when the phenomenon to be studied is large and complex and cannot be considered outside the context in which it naturally occurs. It is an empirical study that seeks to determine or test a theory and has interviews as one of the most important sources of information. Through them, the interviewee expresses his opinion on a given subject, using his interpretations.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The survey covered the universe of twenty-one special education professionals, who were invited to respond to a questionnaire containing about twenty-two objective questions and one subjective, and their results were analyzed throughout the entire process. SEARCHED POPULATION Teachers who work in special education and at the CEPI Alfredo Nasser State School, located at Avenida Prefeito Manoel Lemos de Mendonça s/nº Setor Oeste, Morrinhos – GO.

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

Data collection was carried out by applying a questionnaire and analyzing the reports of professionals who worked in the area of inclusion and special education. The questionnaire was answered by teachers who work in the AEE at the school and sought, from this data collection, to cover as many considerations as possible so that no pertinent question was left unaddressed.

DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE

Data were analyzed using the Excel program. The tabulation of the data allows checking the trends shown when the data are gathered, bringing to light the reality of a given situation

CONCLUSION

Certain that it wouldn't be easy, the teachers from

Apoio and AEE began to fight for innovative and more attractive resources.

And even before this unique situation, we had students without an internet connection and unmotivated, which was aggravated by this pandemic situation because, in addition to teachers having difficulties in presenting online classes and dealing with technological tools, doubts arose about how to attract students. students and also about evaluating the class.

Logically, when working with classes that have students with disabilities, the challenges are even greater, and it is necessary to think of efficient ways to communicate with them at a distance and, above all, how to present accessible content, among other details.

As not all students have access to computers and cell phones, it was necessary to resort to family members, creating a group with students and working with them through video calls and sending activities via WhatsApp to parents and the teacher himself set up an individual time to help the student. to respond online.

It is important to include the context in which I, the researcher, am being inserted. I started working in education in 1994, when I passed a public contest in the city of Morrinhos, State of Goiás. I worked at the Alfredo Nasser State School, the first Reference School for Inclusion in Morrinhos to receive special students as a literacy teacher and also as a facilitator of the Educational Informatics Laboratory (LIE) and Pedagogical Coordinator.

I worked as a Special Education Coordinator at the Regional Undersecretary of Education, in 2018, I returned to my duties as a Special Education teacher at the Alfredo Nasser State School.

Every barrier that a student with a disability encounters in the classroom is also encountered in distance learning. And this difficulty is often aggravated by the lack of preparation of the families of these children and young people, who, in addition to having to teach the given subject, must deal with the specificity of each student. 88 Each child has its characteristics and differences. There is no standard to be used with all children. The cases must be observed with a singular look,

not as a whole. In addition to the help of mediators, many students undergo continuous treatment with therapists, psycho-pedagogues, and speech therapists, in parallel so that they can follow the teaching in classrooms. It is noticeable that the use of assistive technologies contributed to the development of remote classes in 2020 and has much more to contribute in the coming years.

However, for professionals to be more confident when teaching their classes and for their students to be able to better absorb what is given to them, greater initiatives are needed.

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THE INSERTION OF LIBRAS IN THE EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT: THE POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION IN THE INITIAL YEARS AND IN THE NATIONAL EXAMINATION OF HIGH EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article brings about the insertion of Libras in the educational context, with a possibility of implementation in the early years and the National Secondary Education Examination (ENEM), in which it is part of the curricular teaching proposals, however, the language is not inserted of signs, making it relevant for the development of learning and even for hearing and deaf children, with the aim of a permanent construction at school, which needs to be valued in order to establish a democratic and inclusive environment. The general aim was to analyze the inclusion of Libras in the initial years and in the national exam of secondary education as an important instrument in the educational context. Methodologically, this article had a qualitative approach and bibliographical research, contextualizing through articles, books, legislation, academic works, and important subjects that lead to understanding about the insertion of pounds in the initial years and in the national exam of secondary education as a mere important instrument in the educational context. Therefore, it is concluded that some do not include Sign Language as a subject in basic education, especially in PNC. However, observing the DCN, it is noted that its guidelines bring about Libras in a different way, in which they promote it as an important sign language for the integration and inclusion of hearing and deaf people. Despite these instruments not being very effective, it is analyzed that it shows the possibility of implementation for this teaching.

Keywords: Educational context. Pounds. Early Years. National High School Exam.

INTRODUCTION

The process of Libras's insertion in the educational context was an important perspective of creation throughout Brazil, giving as a referred instrument that arose from the need for communication of deaf people. In view of the initial years and the ENEM, it is part of the teaching curriculum proposals, however, sign language is not inserted, in which it is relevant for the development of learning and even for hearing children, to of a permanent construction in the school, which needs to be valued in order to establish a democratic and inclusive environment. Therefore, the justification for this theme emerged from preliminary investigations and shared experiences in the school community, in which Libras in the educational context is an instrument that has a valuable role for deaf individuals and teachers. Also, enabling and implementing it in the ENEM curriculum and in the initial years, this practice will bring a marked difference in educational policies, mainly linguistic, due to the inclusion and respect for Law nº 10.436/2002. Based on this assumption, the issue at hand is why the inclusion of Libras in the early years and in the national exam of secondary education is important for the educational context.

This research intends, as a general aim, to analyze the inclusion of Libras in the initial years and in the national exam of secondary education as an important instrument in the educational context. As for the specific objectives, they are to understand the importance of Libras in the educational context; understand the documents of Brazilian educational policies and Libras; discuss about the possibilities of implementing Libras in the initial years and in the National High School Examination.

Methodologically, throughout this article a qualitative approach and bibliographical research were used, contextualizing through articles, books, legislation, academic works, and important subjects that lead to understanding about the insertion of Libras in the initial years and in the national exam of secondary education as a mere important instrument in the educational context.

This article is divided into three sections, the first of which is about the importance of Libras in the educational context, which through its instrument makes several individuals in the school environment

have their communication of development in learning. The second section elaborated on the documents of Brazilian educational policies and Libras, which show the relevance of stimulating learning in the most accessible way in educational institutions, seeking approaches permeated in new learning. The third brings about the possibilities of implementing Libras in the early years and in the National High School Examination, considering the best succinct way to start the teaching stage.

Therefore, the relevance of this article stems from the question of the insertion of Libras aimed at establishing the knowledge present in the early years of elementary school and in ENEM, which will bring a present focus on communication between listeners and the deaf, and citizens.

THE IMPORTANCE OF LIBRAS IN THE EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT

From French Sign Language, Brazilian Sign Language emerged, starting in Brazil, the first school for the deaf, in 1856, with the support of D Pedro II and the collaboration of the French teacher of the deaf Eduard Huet. In 1857, in Rio de Janeiro, the Collégio Nacional for Deaf-Mutes, currently the National Institute of Education for the Deaf (INES), was founded, in which he began to teach students who lived in that city. In fact, in the 1980s, this language, through the Bill, became legalized and recognized by Law No. 10,436 on April 24, 2002.

Deafness has always been considered, as well as any disability, a curse that threw the man into limbo or death for identifying him as incapable. And this, for not resembling the normality grouped in time and space, is not only excluded by the spiritual context but also by the economic partner in different cultures, as Duarte explains (2013, p. 1715), "knowledge and reflection on the spaces and times that shaped the history of the deaf – ranging from sacrifices in public squares, reclusion in institutions, integrationist policies to current discourses of inclusion".

Costa (2022) emphasizes that "Law 10.436/2002, which makes Libras official as an official language and gives the Deaf person the right to have a quality education, brings out the importance of teaching Libras in the early years of the Deaf child",

enabling educational and social inclusion, due to its integration with the language itself, which facilitates learning and communication in this environment.

Soon, then, through Decree nº 5.626, of December 22, 2005, the inclusion of Libras was inserted as a curricular subject for the deaf community, with Portuguese as a second language, as well as the training of bilingual teachers, among other aspects, making it clear that this instrument in the educational context has become important for inclusive practices, both in schools and in society, providing the cognitive and linguistic development of all individuals with deafness, in order to facilitate the learning process (BAIENSE; SILVA, 2022).

In this way, Libras are placed as a form of language that promotes social inclusion and communication in society for individuals with deafness. Its importance in the school environment must be highlighted, as it allows these subjects to have acceptance and development in learning, guaranteeing the preservation of their community through this language. Therefore, in the educational context, this language enables people to communicate in the social environment, developing their professional and educational skills.

ANALYSIS OF BRAZILIAN EDUCATIONAL POLICY DOCUMENTS AND LIBRAS

As previously seen, Libras focuses on the obligation of the most varied curricular disciplines, within the context of the needs of deaf and hearing people. Reflecting on education brings a direction for learning, as well as determinations that are listed in the modality brought by the National Curriculum Parameters - PNC. This document had its reflexive changes, in which it institutes linguistic recognition. As the PNC determines that:

Obligatorily to provide opportunities for the study of the Portuguese language, mathematics, the physical and natural world, and the social and political reality, emphasizing knowledge of Brazil. The teaching of Art and Physical Education are also compulsory curricular areas, necessarily integrated into the pedagogical proposal. The teaching of

at least one modern foreign language becomes a mandatory curricular component, from the fifth grade of elementary school onwards (PNC, 1997, p.14).

The PNC does not have information on the teaching of Sign Languages; however, this document is attached to the other languages for teaching, discussing the National Curriculum Guidelines - DCN, in which it adds Law nº 9.795/99, providing for the National Policy of Environmental Education and Law No. 10,436/2002, which provides for the Brazilian Sign Language (LIBRAS). In view of this, the guidelines present special needs, bringing the language of Libras in a different way. According to inc. 3, students must have access to its contents, “through the use of applicable languages and codes, such as the Braille system, the Brazilian Sign Language (LIBRAS) and assistive technology [...]” (BRASIL, 2013, p. 407).

The Law of Guidelines and Bases - LDB also states that it will be “given in Portuguese, assured to indigenous communities and the use of their mother tongues and learning processes” (BRASIL, 1996). In this way, the insertion of Libras became one of the perspectives for the use of interpreters, teachers, among others, in which it evidenced, among other languages, the communication between hearing and deaf people, passing as a form of visual language based on hand gestures. and body and facial expression, which leads thousands of people to want to understand and learn Sign Language, to exchange experiences, aiming at integration and inclusion between hearing and deaf people.

THE POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTING LIBRAS IN THE INITIAL YEARS AND IN THE NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL EXAMINATION

In 1998, the ENEM was instituted, aiming to evaluate the school performance of students during the end of basic education, which, in 2009, was improved with a new methodology, starting to use mechanisms for access to higher education. Since then, in 2020, the participant has chosen to take the printed or digital exam, applying tests through computers, in institutions defined by the National Institute of Educational Studies and Research Anísio Teixeira - Inep.

With this, it is verified how recent this Decree is, as stated by Kumada and Pietro (2019, p. 81), “after the regulation of Libras and the establishment of the training of professionals to teach this language system, reality still reflects a great need in the area”. The Enem is also administered in Libras for the deaf and hearing-impaired community who only have Libras as their first language, in which the participant needs to request the appeal via video test with an additional time of up to 120 minutes on each day of the test. On the other hand, this evaluation for the listeners is not inserted as a discipline, making it clear that it presents a lack of inclusion for the knowledge of the listeners. Above all, these issues become relevant to expand learning in educational institutions, aiming at the integration of this language dynamics for all individuals. Soon,

The important thing, therefore, is that students appropriate the specificities of each language, without losing sight of the whole in which they are inserted. More than that, it is important that they understand that languages are dynamic and that everyone participates in this process of constant transformation (BRASIL, 2018, p. 63).

Understanding how ENEM proposes its assessment methods contributes to a perspective that should be revised, inserting a national policy to measure students’ knowledge following education guidelines, in an idealized margin that involves all disciplines, including sign language. When referring to the early years of elementary school, this language should also be considered essential for learning. In view of this, enabling this implementation in these stages may constitute an expansion in the interaction of languages between hearing and deaf people.

The reinvention of the ENEM as a selective process to replace the entrance exam would support and help democratize access to the university, which, together with the subsequent system of the quota program, would allow the inclusion of different social groups and the expansion of higher education services. This, therefore, would make the Enem an ambivalent instrument, being used whether at the entrance to technical or higher-level courses and

at the same time also used to assess the skills and abilities acquired by students at the secondary level. In the Incorporation of the function of admitting and distributing vacancies in public and private universities, ENEM promotes the modification of cultural subjectivity, in economic and social relations, as well as re-elaborates a common base of norms and content for High School (PIAIA, 2013). Therefore, based on this understanding, there is a mistake in documents about Libras, which is a mother tongue that should be recognized as a school subject, which could be inserted in the early years of elementary school and ENEM, along with the other languages, and not as a playful method of gestures, while there is a need for expansion in learning.

CONCLUSION

To conclude this article, it is known that Libras is an important instrument in educational institutions, officially, a sign language that is proposed for hearing and deaf people, which mediates the communication between both, which, relatively, is considered an evolution that empowers individuals across the country. Among the other questions about this research, it is understood that this sign language is of fundamental relevance for teachers, therefore, its implementation process in the initial years and in ENEM, overcomes a great challenge for those working in this inclusive space.

Thus, it is noted that the importance of Libras in the educational context revolves around a discipline that must be fundamental in the school environment, considering it as an instrument that is available in legislation, being created to facilitate communication in the educational context, as well as, a horizon that can go far beyond a normal path, since learning this language provides the school community with an interactivity that emphasizes the appreciation of deaf people, providing opportunities for communicative interaction between teachers, students, and citizens.

After analyzing the Brazilian educational policies and Libras, it is concluded that some do not insert Sign Language as a subject of basic education, mainly the PNC. However, observing the DCN, it is noted that its guidelines bring about Libras in a different way, in which they promote it as an

important sign language for the integration and inclusion of hearing and deaf people. Despite these instruments not being very effective, it is analyzed that it shows the possibility of implementation for this teaching.

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